

On the Inference of Inclusion Floatation Efficiency in Steelmaking Tundish from RTD Measurements

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INTRODUCTION

Metallurgical performance of steelmaking tundish systems has been frequently investigated through physical and mathematical modelling. In many of these¹⁻⁶, results from Residence time distribution (RTD) measurements have been applied to address, mostly qualitatively, inclusion floatation from tundish systems. It is now generally agreed, *albeit sans* evidence, that large, dispersed plug flow volumes ensure expeditious floatation of inclusion from steelmaking tundish. The hypothesis is tested and evaluated directly in this work through plant scale measurements, carried out on two different bloom casting tundish systems, embodying a recently proposed criterion on inclusion floatation efficiency. In the following, numerical prediction of RTD, plant scale measurements of inclusion floatation efficiency their comparison as well as adequacy of RTD studies towards inclusion floatation are examined.

PRESENT WORK

1. Mathematical Modelling

Many prior studies⁴ have demonstrated that hydrodynamics and tracer dispersion phenomena in steel making tundish systems can be predicted with reasonable certainty through a steady-state, turbulent flow calculation procedure. Accordingly, RANS (Reynolds Average Navier-Stokes) equations in conjunction with a scalar transport model have been applied to predict flow and RTD (residence time distributions) phenomena in the tundish, embodying the standard, $k-\varepsilon$ turbulence model⁷. In the present study, two different versions of the model i.e., homogeneous and two-phase; gas-liquid flows were applied; the latter to primarily to study the influence of aspiration phenomena through shroud on RTD. Two-phase simulations were performed via a VOF (volume of fluid) approach. From the predicted RTD or C curves, corresponding flow volumes were estimated on the basis of mixed and modified mixed flow models, described in detail in ref. 8. Governing equations and associated boundary conditions applicable to steady state, homogeneous as well as two phase turbulent flows in tundish are well known⁴ and therefore, not reproduced here. All computations reported in this study were carried out via the commercial CFD solver, ANSYS⁹ FluentTM 18.0. To optimize the trade-off between solution precision and CPU time, the computational domain was discretized into a large number of non-overlapping volume elements. A sufficiently stringent convergence criterion, $= 5 \times 10^{-4}$, was set on all flow variables for better accuracy. Taking advantage of geometry, only one half of tundish was considered and numerical calculations were carried out embodying 483177 and 204581 number of elements for Plant A and Plant B tundishes respectively.

2. Industrial scale trials

A large number of continuous casting heats were monitored in two different special steel plants producing diverse grades of speciality steels via the EAF-LRF-VD-CC routes. The details of continuous casting operation in the two plants are summarised in Table 1. These are similar capacity plants, use similar casting facilities and produce similar grades of speciality steels. During continuous casting of LCAK (low carbon aluminium killed) steel, liquid steel samples were collected (i) immediately after VD lifting, (ii) from tundish (often as a function of time) as well as (iii) from solidified bloom /slab and subjected to chemical analysis for determination of *total* as well as *dissolved* aluminium, calcium and magnesium. On the basis of such, corresponding changes in composition (i.e., *total* as well as *dissolved* Al, Ca and Mg) between VD lifting and tundish as well as tundish and bloom/slab were inferred. Soluble and total aluminium (also Ca and Mg) contents in steel were determined

through spectroscopy of representative solidified melt samples, using the well-established discriminating criteria. Such techniques, as applied in the industry, are standard and well established. Reliability and reproducibility of measurements were evaluated through many repeat trials, and these are described in ref. 10.

Table I Physical dimensions and operating parameters in continuous bloom casting as practised in two different special steel plants.

Parameters	Plant A	Plant B
Tundish capacity, Tonne	13	7.5
Product type	Bloom	Bloom
Number of strands and shape	3; Delta	2; Delta
Range of throughput rate, kg/min	900-1100	750-850
Shroud internal diameter, mm	53-63	70-67
Shroud separation distance from tundish base, mm	550-570	500-550
Typical estimated shroud submergence time, s	379-546	385-450

3. A formalism for assessment of inclusion floatation efficiency in steelmaking tundish

In a recent work¹⁰, it is shown that on the basis of variations of soluble and total (= soluble +insoluble) aluminium contents in LCAK steel between VD lifting station and solidification (typically the 3rd bloom), an expression for the fractional inclusion floatation, F_I can be readily formulated via material balance and represented as:

$$F_I = \frac{-\Delta wt.\% Al_{sol} + (-\Delta wt.\% Al_{insol})}{(wt.\% Al_{insol,VD} + [-\Delta wt.\% Al_{sol}])} \quad (1)$$

For steel containing Ca and Mg in addition to Al, Eq.(1) can also be generalised to:

$$F_I = \frac{-\sum \Delta wt.\% X_{sol} + \sum (-\Delta wt.\% X_{insol})}{(\sum wt.\% X_{insol,VD} + \sum (-\Delta wt.\% X_{sol}))} \quad (2)$$

in which, X represents Al, Ca and Mg respectively. In Eq.(1), the left hand side i.e., $wt.\% Al_{insol,bloom}$ represents the final insoluble aluminium present in the solidified bloom. Similarly, the right hand side of Eq.(1) embodies three terms representing respectively, (i) insoluble aluminium present at VD lifting station, (ii) change in dissolved Aluminium in steel between bloom and VD, which is equivalent to insoluble aluminium generation due to re-oxidation of soluble aluminium in tundish and (iii) removal of insoluble aluminium from tundish via floatation. Therefore, it is apparent that negative of dissolved aluminium fading i.e., $\Delta wt.\% Al_{sol}$ (defined in this work according to: $wt.\% Al_{sol,bloom} - wt.\% Al_{sol,VD}$) represents corresponding generation of new insoluble aluminium in tundish. In this work, insoluble aluminium and alumina inclusions are treated synonymously, *albeit*, in a qualitative sense. The material balance scheme implicit in the derivation of F_I is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 The scheme of a chemistry-based estimation of inclusion floatation index via material balance on dissolved and total aluminium content change due to floatation and reoxidation in tundish under steady state operating conditions

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Predicted dispersed plug flow volume fractions in the two tundish systems under different operating conditions (at minimum and maximum throughput rate with and without air aspiration through shroud) deduced from respective RTD via two different flow models⁸ are illustrated in Fig.2. These indicate that irrespective of operating conditions and procedure adopted to estimate flow volumes⁸, proportions of dispersed plug flow volume in the two tundish systems are comparable, with Plant B tundish having somewhat higher estimates. Such trends are not entirely unexpected given the similarity of tundish operating parameters (i.e., flow rates, capacity and shapes, flow modifiers etc.) in the two plants. As a first approximation, one might therefore consider natural floatation tendency of inclusions or, inclusion *floatation efficiency* F_1 in the two tundish systems to be very similar.

Figure 2 Plug/dispersed plug flow volumes in the two industrial tundish systems (disregarding gas aspiration in shroud) via two different formalisms based on a homogeneous turbulent flow calculation procedure.

To assess the above on the basis of direct plant scale measurements, compositions of steel (primarily dissolved and total aluminium), monitored at different stages of continuous casting (i.e., VD lifting and solidified blooms), were applied and fractional inclusion floatation or, inclusion floatation index F_1 , in the two tundish systems, estimated via Eq.1 for identical grades of steel. The results thus obtained are shown in Fig. 3. This evidently corroborates the trend of RTD results shown in Fig.2 suggesting essentially that inclusion floatation efficiency in the two tundish systems is very similar. Interestingly, Fig.2 is also indicative of relatively higher average values of inclusion floatation efficiency index F_1 in the Plant B tundish, and this is identical to the inference one would draw from RTD results presented in Fig.2. Correspondence between Fig.2 and 3 therefore as a distinct possibility suggests that dispersed plug flow volume fraction is a key characteristic of melt flow in tundish and exerts dominating effect on inclusion floatation.

Figure 3 Comparison of inclusion floatation efficiency in the two industrial tundish systems as inferred on the basis of direct measurements of melt and bloom chemistry.

The computational results presented in Fig.2 were derived based on a single-phase flow formulation, disregarding any gas aspiration through ladle shroud. However, it is well known that during industrial continuous casting process, gases (air +argon) are invariably aspirated through shroud, result in two-phase, gas-liquid flows known to flows of steel in tundish and the associated residence time distributions. This important aspect of steel transfer operation from ladle and its attendant influence on RTD was rarely addressed in physical and mathematical modelling study of continuous casting tundish system reported so far so far.

Numerical simulation of fluid flow phenomena with a VOF based turbulent flow model indicates that gas aspiration through shroud influences flow field and hence the tracer dispersion phenomena in tundish. The flow fields generated in the three- strand, Plant-A tundish, with and without gas aspiration, are presented in Fig.4 (a) and (b) respectively. These clearly indicate that aspirated gas reduces the penetration of the incoming jet, due to buoyancy of the upwelling mixture, leading to a flow pattern in the tundish that is substantially different from the one in which, no gas is aspirated in shroud. It is also apparent from the computational results that aspiration through shroud tends to retard melt flow and produces more diffused, uniform liquid flows towards tundish outlets. Indeed, corresponding RTD curves, presented immediately below in Fig.5, clearly indicate a delayed peak as well as substantially more spread of the RTD in the case of air aspiration through shroud.

Figure 4 Predicted velocity field in the three strand tundish (Plant A) along the central transverse plane (a) without air aspiration and (b) with air aspiration ($Q_G/Q_L = 0.1$) as predicted via a VOF based turbulent flow model.

As a final point, prediction of size specific inclusion generation and removal or, residual inclusion content in melt, necessitate more advanced, physically based models than is afforded by RTD. Despite such, relative trends of inclusion floatation can be obtained from simplistic RTD studies as the present study has demonstrated. It is therefore legitimate to carry out performance comparison of different tundish systems having different tundish designs, flow modifiers etc., as is currently the practice, via physical and mathematical modelling of RTD.

Figure 5 Numerically predicted C curves in the three strand (Plant A) tundish illustrating the influence of gas aspiration phenomena via shroud on RTD as predicted via a VOF based turbulent flow model.

CONCLUSIONS

Inclusion floatation efficiency in steelmaking tundish systems has been investigated on the basis of RTD and plant scale measurements. Variation in dispersed plug flow volumes deduced from RTD corroborates the trends of industrial scale measurements and suggests that relative inclusion floatation efficiency of different tundish systems and their comparative metallurgical performance can be adequately inferred from physical and mathematical modelling of RTD.

REFERENCES

1. Y. Sahai and T. Emi, "Tundish Technology for clean steel production", World Scientific Publishing Co. Ltd. USA, 2007, p.1.
2. O.J. Ilegbusi and Szekely, "The Physical and Mathematical Modelling of Tundish Operations", Springer-Verlag, New-York, 1989, p..1
3. J. Schade, "Tundish Metallurgy", ISS of AIME, 1991, p.1.
4. D.Mazumdar and R.I.L. Guthrie," The physical and mathematical modelling of steelmaking tundish system" ISIJ International, Vol.39, 1999, p.524.
5. E. Martinez, M. Maeda, L.J. Heaslip, G. Rodriguez, and A. McLean, "Effect of fluid flow on the inclusion separation in tundish", Trans. ISIJ, Vol..26 1986, p.24.
6. B. Yang, H. Lei, Y. Xu, K. Liu and P. Han, "Numerical Investigation of Flow Characteristics of Molten Steel in the Tundish with Channel Induction Heating", Metals, vol.11, 2021, p.1.
7. B.E. Launder and D.B. Spalding, "The numerical computation of turbulent flows", Comp. Methods in App. Mech. and Engg., Vol.3, 1974, p.269.
8. Y. Sahai and T. Emi T, "Melt flow characterisation in continuous casting tundishes", ISIJ International, Vol.36, 1996, p.667.
9. ANSYS™ Fluent, Theory Guide, version 12.0, ANSYS Inc, Canonsburg, (2009).
10. D.Mazumdar, "Tundish process performance parameters and their direct estimation from a new, plant measurement-based formalism", Metallurgical and Materials Transactions B, Vol.52,2021 p.23.